

METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF CREATING A HEALTHY AND CREATIVE ENVIRONMENT IN THE ADMINISTRATIVE ACTIVITY OF THE HEAD OF AN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION

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Annotation: Explores the complex psychological characteristics that contribute to successful relationships between leaders and employees in management settings. By reviewing existing literature, applying various research methods, and presenting key findings, the study aims to shed light on the critical aspects that foster positive and effective work relationships between leaders and their team members.

Key words: psychological characteristics, management, workplace dynamics, leadership.

Standard unit of responsibility, control technique (i.e. information-computing technique and teaching-methodical technology and financial documents), control procedure (pedagogic meetings, councils, meetings...), control environment (school teaching staff, the student body of study groups, dormitory students), analysis systems (psychological and pedagogical diagnostics, reports...) and planning. Control is one of the main functions of management, which is to ensure the achievement of the goals set by the organization, to implement the management decisions made. With its help, the management of the supervisory organization determines the correctness of decisions and determines the need to correct them. Implementation of control, on the one hand, means setting standards, achieving results and measuring them, deviations from established standards; on the other hand, action monitoring is the implementation of the management decisions made and the evaluation of the results achieved during their implementation. It is the control results that are the basis for the organization's managers to correct the previously made decisions, if there are significant deviations in the implementation of the previously made decisions. The control system allows you to identify these positive aspects and the strengths identified in the implementation of its activities. By comparing the actual results with the planned results, the management of the organization will be able to determine where the organization has succeeded and where it has failed. Types of control. Any management function can be effective only when there is an effective control system. Management is a very important and complex task management, but it is unpleasant for company employees. One of the most important control features to consider first is that control must be comprehensive. Control cannot remain a privilege only for the manager and his assistants appointed by the "controller". Every manager, regardless of level, should exercise control as an integral part of his duties, even if no one has specifically assigned him.

All types of control are similar because they have the same goal: to ensure that the results actually obtained are as close as possible to what is desired. They differ only in the implementation time. Initial control. This type of control is called preliminary, because it is carried out before the actual start of work. The most important types of control in an

organization should be camouflaged among other management functions. Thus, for example, the planning and creation of organizational structures is rare. The main means of implementation of initial control is the implementation of certain rules, procedures and directions of behavior. Because rules and lines of conduct are designed to ensure that following through on plans, sticking to them is a way to make sure that the work is done in a certain direction. If you write clear job descriptions, effectively communicate the formulation of goals to your subordinates, and attract qualified people to the administrative management apparatus, this will increase the likelihood that the organizational structure will work as intended. Current control is performed directly during operation.

Most often, its object is subordinate employees, and it itself is traditionally the right of their direct boss. Regular inspection of subordinates' work, discussion of emerging problems and proposals for improving work excludes deviations from planned plans and instructions. If these deviations are allowed to develop, they can become serious difficulties for the entire organization.

Current control is literally not carried out at the same time as the work itself. On the contrary, it is based on measuring the actual results obtained after directed work to achieve the desired goals. In order to carry out current control in this way, the control apparatus needs feedback. Feedback is the exchange of information about the results obtained. The simplest example of feedback is a boss telling his subordinates that if he sees it, their work is unsatisfactory, they are wrong. Feedback systems allow the management to determine the presence of unexpected problems and adjust yourself in order not to deviate from the organization's line of behavior and the most effective way to the tasks set before it.

Final control - compare the actually obtained results with the desired ones, either immediately after being under control or after a predetermined time. Although final control is implemented too late to respond to problems as they arise, it also has two important functions:

Tashkilot rahbariyatiga quyidagilar uchun zarur bo'lgan ma'lumotlarni beradib agar shunga o'xshash ishlar kelajakda amalga oshirilishi kerak bo'lsa, rejalashtirish. Aslida olingan va talab qilingan natijalarni taqqoslab, rahbariyat qay darajada ekanligini baholash imkoniyatiga ega uning rejalari realist edi. Ushbu protsedura quyidagilarga imkon beradi shuningdek, yuzaga kelgan muammolar haqida ma'lumot oling va kelajakda ushbu muammolarni oldini olish uchun yangi rejalarni tuzing; motivatsiyaga yordam beradi. Agar tashkilot rahbariyati motivatsion mukofotlarni ma'lum bir yutuq bilan bog'lasa ishlash darajasi, demak, aniq erishilgan samaradorlik aniq va ob'ektiv ravishda o'lchanishi kerak. Boshqaruv nazoratining mohiyati va maqsadi erishilgan natijalarni rejalashtirilgan maqsadlar bilan o'zaro bog'lashdir. Tor ma'noda nazoratning maqsadi-boshqaruv ob'ektining axborot shaffofligi samarali qarorlar qabul qilish imkoniyati uchun. Boshqaruv nazorat hamma uchun mavjud bo'lgan asos xarakterini oladi va barcha bosqichlarda boshqaruv jarayonining maqbul yo'nalishini ta'minlaydi: rejalashtirish, tashkil etish, tartibga solish, hisobga olish va tahlil qilish. Joriy, tematik, yakuniy, davriy qayd etiladi.

The task of management control is to evaluate and test knowledge, skills and abilities of students or students, as well as the professional competence of their teachers. The peculiarity of supervision is determined by the presence of two types of training: general education and professional. Many teachers control methods include: oral tests (conversation, story, seminar, mutual control, etc.), written tests (abstracts, control and independent works; graphic tests (diagrams, drawings, tables); practical work (experiments, laboratory developments); control content should determine the quality of development of students (students) according to the educational standard to

ensure the quality of the school education system, to create a creative educational institution, to claim that it is an integral element of the management process; at all stages A "separate" stage that provides quality information in the management process. T. I. Shamova offers an almost convenient type of management. V. A. Slastenin, I. F. Isayev, who or what is being managed the following are distinguished depending on: personal control; class-generalizer; thematic general; complex-generalizing. In the practice of schools, a certain tradition has developed in determining the quality of knowledge: oral examination, written examination and practical.

Control tools can be tasks or a system of tasks aimed at determining learning outcomes: tests, dictations, questions for written, control and practical work; The result of such control is the assessment of students' knowledge or

students, marking. In addition, evaluation is a process that determines the quality of activities (or actions) performed by teachers, heads of educational institutions. Designation is the result of this process, their conditional formal (quantitative) reflection. Assessment of knowledge can be personal (compared with knowledge), comparative (with other classmates or classmates), normative (with criteria, norms, requirements). In practice, comparative evaluation prevails. The legal basis of the management of the educational institution is formed from it.

Rules are a document that determines the order of actions and instructions for solving certain aspects of the activity of an educational institution. Normative documents issued by the director of the educational institution within the framework of its authority, on the basis of orders, regulations and execution, recommendations, letters (notes), proposals and other types of assignments are not included in the normative legal documents of the educational institution. the principals, including in written form. The charter of the educational institution; rules of internal procedure; Pedagogical Council, Methodical Council, Board of Trustees of System Rules, Assessment of knowledge about paid services, rent, extra-budgetary activities, etc. constitute the system of local regulatory legal documents of the institution.

At the same time, there are a number of shortcomings in the existing management control system in modern educational institutions: the interruption of the assessment of the educational system that occurs by force, the lack of an appropriate mechanism of intermediate, border or current control at each stage of education; the predominance of final control carried out by one teacher, which leads to subjectivity - an inherent feature of the evaluation process; the impossibility of describing only parts of knowledge, skills, abilities and determining the overall picture of educational results; lack of individual approach due to the fact that the teacher does not fully know the personal characteristics of each student, etc.

Regulation and control is a complex and difficult task. First of all, it is related to the system of relationships between children, adults and the combination of these relationships: "student-student", "principal-student", etc. The process of interaction systems, the educational process of determining the criteria of different parties, regulatory systems explains the complexity of management and management functions. Control is necessary at the stages of management activities. Supervision within the school should be carried out by professionals, professionals, there is no reason to doubt their objectivity and open opinions. Control should be carried out regularly. Usually, the leader makes a plan schedule within the school to control. Control or inspection work can be planned for use by the administration of the educational institution. In accordance with the thematic plan, the teacher of this or that subject determines the time of supervision activities in which the principal or the deputy principal for educational affairs can participate. It is appropriate that the teacher knew about the upcoming control by the administration. Thus, the auditor's professionalism, objectivity,

systematicity are the main requirements for the implementation of control. Benevolence in the process of control, showing interest in educational activities is equally important for teachers and students. In educational conditions, the management control process does not limit creative initiative, but is determined by scientifically proven criteria. The objective criteria of teachers' educational activity are positive, professional, important psychophysical and personality changes, the qualities of students (students) and the level of knowledge acquisition by them. is that the subject of skill in the student's educational activity is the road leading to skills, analysis of the road, "the method of education itself is action", proverbial sign and its stimuli not. The activity-based approach in continuous education is not only for acquiring knowledge, but also for the methods of this assimilation, patterns and methods of thinking and activity, the development of the student's cognitive powers and creative potential. This approach opposes the oral methods and forms of dogmatic transfer of ready-made information, the monologic and impersonality of oral teaching, the passivity of teaching, finally, the uselessness of knowledge, skills and abilities that cannot be implemented in reality.

¹ Therefore, control should also be carried out in the following ways: knowledge acquisition, ways of thinking and activities of subjects in the educational process. Management activity was formed and developed during all stages of educational development. It is important to note that it is important at all stages of continuing education, from kindergarten to higher education, post-graduate studies and doctoral studies. The role of management is very high. This ensures a normal development process of a person - as a full-fledged person. The essence of comprehensive management of training of students (students) is in the unity of solving problems of improving the educational, educational and cognitive process, scientific research and self-management of students (students), Management efficiency is the interaction of managers and managers. successfully solve the problems faced by the team, depending on the secret, social and psychological climate in the team, the direction of the personality of each member of the team, and the desire. In the process of pedagogical interactions with students (students), the teacher's actions are determined by a whole complex of internal and external factors. The influence of these factors and their objective value are variable. They depend on individual differences.

between teachers and from the specific situation in which the pedagogical process takes place. It is relatively easy to observe the factors affecting the external activity of the teacher.

At the same time, management action in any sphere of life, if it exists, is carried out by the necessary number of necessary performers and the level of competence; includes a motivational principle that encourages employees to participate in the implementation of this decision. Interest in management in the educational system not only did not dry up, but on the contrary: new textbooks continue to appear on the management process and its global importance for pedagogy and people. Management actions and management control emancipation of the educational process should not hinder the creative initiative of teachers, should not wear thoughtless whims or self-judgment, but determined by scientifically proven criteria.

¹ANAKINA A.F (ANALIZ SOBSTIVENISTI PRADUKTA) MASKVA :1995 264-B

orientation to increase. Diversity means creating conditions of choice in the educational system and giving opportunities to each subject at the right time; encourage students (students) to make independent choices and make responsible decisions, ensure the development of flexible and independent thinking.

Multi-level is the organization of a multi-level educational process that provides the opportunity to reach the level of education that matches the capabilities and interests of a person at each stage of education. Each level is a period with its own goals, study time and characteristics. Fundamentalization-strengthening the relationship between theoretical and practical preparation of a young man for modern life.

Informatization of education is associated with the wide and increasing use of computer technologies and information technologies in the process of human education. Informatization has become more common throughout the world in the last decade, due to the availability of images for the system and the relative simplicity of using various temporary video audio equipment and computers.

Individualization is taking into account and developing the individual characteristics of students and students in all forms of interaction with them in the process of education and training. Continuity refers to the process of continuous education and self-education throughout a person's life due to rapidly developing living conditions in modern society. One of the distinctive features of the modern education system is the transition from state to state-to-social management of education. The main idea of state-social management is to unite the efforts of the state and society in solving educational problems, to help teachers, students, and parents in choosing the content, forms and methods of organizing the educational process, in different types of education. is to give more rights and freedoms in choosing lim institutions. The choice of rights and freedoms as a person makes a person not only an object of education, but also its active subject, who independently chooses a wide range of programs, educational institutions, and types of relationships.

The Law of the Russian Federation "On Education" declares the democratic, sovereign-social nature of management and the autonomy of educational institutions as the main principles of state policy.

State and public management is a management that combines the activities of state and public management entities. Undoubtedly, the state and public administration should not adopt or replace all structures of education management, should not make their arithmetic sum. Several stages of formation and implementation of the idea of continuous education can be noted:

-The phenomenological stage (late 70s-early 80s) is carried out by understanding continuing education as adult education, which is a component of additional education.- Conceptual stage (mid-80s - The beginning of the 90s) is characterized by the deepening of the idea of continuous education, which became the development of the "concept of continuous education" (1989).

- Theoretical stage (early 90s - late 90s) development of aspect systems of continuous education (economic, natural-mathematical, ecological, etc.), formation of Real continuous education systems in practice, including multifunctional, multi It is characterized by the formation of multi-disciplinary and multi-level educational institutions.

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